

Classical Free Particle Lagrangian, Special Relativity and Quantum Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 15, 2022

It is known that classical waves such as waves on a string, sound and light (from Maxwell's em equations) take the argument $-Et+px$ where E is associated with a frequency and p with $1/\text{wavelength}$. We argue that these classical nonrelativistic treatments already bring in features of special relativity (as does Schrodinger equation quantum mechanics for a free particle) as $-Et+px$ is a Lorentz invariant. In fact we argue that Lagrangian formalism: $E=pv-L$ and $p=dL/dv$ is compatible with special relativity. In a previous note (1) we argued that d/dx partial $A(x,t) = p$ and d/dt partial $A(x,t) = -E$ for a free particle with $A=tL(v)$. We also noted that $A=-Et+px$ is a solution, but that one may also write $E(v)= E(x/t)$ and $p(x/t)$ and take the derivatives d/dx partial A and d/dt partial A and obtain the same results. In this note we show how this follows from regular Lagrange theory and note that one already associates d/dx partial with p and d/dt partial with $-E$ i.e. the quantum theory for a free particle is present.

Special Relativity

We argue that special relativity is present in seemingly nonrelativistic physics. For example, classical wave solutions including waves on a string, light from Maxwell's em equations and sound are of the form $\cos(-Et+px)$ where E is usually thought of as a frequency and p as related to $1/\text{wavelength}$. The Schrodinger quantum solution for a free particle also contains this form. $-E+px$ is a Lorentz invariant i.e. a dot product. We have argued in a previous note that one may determine $E(v)$ and $p(v)$ from standard Lagrangian equations $E=pv-L$ and $dL/dv=p$ if one uses $p=Ev$ as well. In particular one writes a differential equation linear in dL/dv and solves for L . This yields $E=m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$) and $p=Ev$. If one begins with a particle at rest with m_0 being rest energy one may define a transformation matrix (the Lorentz matrix) for the vector (p,E) namely:

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1/\sqrt{1-vv} & v/\sqrt{1-vv} \\ v/\sqrt{1-vv} & 1/\sqrt{1-vv} \end{vmatrix} \quad ((1))$$

We chose v to be in the direction of the particle. The frame would have velocity $-v$ which is usually seen in equations.

This matrix is unitary using the $-aa+bb$ dot product rule. If one applies this to other vectors, say (x,t) then: $-Et+px$ should be an invariant. To test this consider $(0, m_0)$ and $(0,t)$ in a certain frame. With motion one sees that x',t' is no longer $0,t$ i.e.

$$t' = t/\sqrt{1-vv} \quad x' = vt/\sqrt{1-vv} \quad \text{and} \quad p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv} \quad E = m_0/\sqrt{1-vv} \quad ((2))$$

Calculating $-Et' + px' = m_0t$ i.e. one has an invariant.

Furthermore one may note that:

$$x'/t' = v \text{ and } p/E=v$$

The result $x'/t' = v$ is important for establishing quantum mechanical results from a classical Lagrangian.

Flow/Flux Equations

In (1) we argued that flow/flux equations for a free particle (relativistic or nonrelativistic, rest mass or no rest mass):

$$d/dx (\text{partial}) A(x,t) = p \text{ and } d/dt (\text{partial}) A(x,t) = -E \quad ((3))$$

are equivalent to the Lagrangian formalism $E=pv-L$ and $dL/dv=p$. These equations are important in that they link p to d/dx and E to d/dt which is already quantum mechanics for a free particle. In order for these equations to apply we make use of the idea that v in the Lorentz transformation is equivalent to x'/t' (starting with the vector $(0,t)$).

One may see that a solution of ((3)) is $A = -Et+px = t L(v)$ where L is the relativistic or nonrelativistic free particle Lagrangian.. This holds for classical waves as well although $p=Ev$ does not. Thus ((3)) and the following pertain to both particles with and without rest mass. The Lorentz transformation ((2)) also holds for both.

In (1), we showed that one may write $L(x/t)$. This follows because $v=x'/t'$. We wish to show here that $A = -E(v)t + p(v)x$ with $v=x/t$ still yields ((3)).

$$\text{Consider } d/dx (\text{partial}) A = p + -dE/v (t/t) + dp/dv (x/t)$$

From the Lagrange result: $E=pv-L$ or $dE/dv = v dp/dv$. Thus:

$$d/dx (\text{partial}) A(x,t) = p \text{ even with } v \text{ replaced with } x/t \text{ and derivatives then taken.}$$

$$\text{For } d/dt (\text{partial}) A(x,t) = -E + t dE/dv (-x/tt) + dp/dv (xx/-tt) = -E$$

Thus, the idea of using $d/dt (\text{partial})$ for E and $d/dx (\text{partial})$ for p already holds for classical waves (sound, light, waves on a string) as well as for quantum mechanics for a free particle which is directly linked to special relativity and Lagrangian formalism.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the presence of $-Et+px$ in classical waves and nonrelativistic quantum mechanics already has its roots in special relativity. We argue these roots are found in the two flux/flow equations for a free particle (relativistic or nonrelativistic, rest mass or no rest mass): $d/dx (\text{partial}) A = p$ and $d/dt (\text{partial}) A = -E$. An immediate solution is $A = -Et+px$, but one may also write $E(v)$ and $p(v)$ with $v=x/t$ and take partial derivatives and obtain the same

equations. We show in this note why this is so by using Lagrangian formalism. We note that if one starts with $(0,t)$ then this transforms under a Lorentz transformation to (x',t') such that $x'/t'=v$. Thus one may already write flux/flow equations which are compatible with Lagrangian formalism and special relativity which describe free particle p in terms of d/dx partial and E in terms of d/dt partial. In other words one has the beginnings of quantum mechanics for a free particle. These may be combined with $E^2=p^2+m^2$ to yield the Klein Gordon equation for a particle with rest mass.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Klein-Gordon Equations, $\exp(i\text{Action})$ (propagator) and Fluctuations (preprint, zenodo, 2021)